

EMOTIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE PRINCIPALS OF COLLEGES OF EDUCATION: A CORRELATION STUDY

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Abstract:

Descriptive Survey Method has been adopted for the conduct of the study. Emotional Competency Inventory for Teachers (Balasubramanian and Abilash Babu, 2009) has been used to collect the required data from the sample chosen. The inventory contains 20 positive items and 5 negative items. The number of items selected for the inventory falling under four major dimensions viz. Self-Awareness, Self-Management, Social Awareness and Relationship Management. In line with the Stratified Random Sampling Technique, 50 Principals of Colleges of Education from three districts of Tamilnadu state have been chosen for the study. Descriptive, differential and correlation analysis have been undertaken for data analysis adopting appropriate statistical techniques. It is found that there is significant difference at 0.05 level between the means of the scores of the Principals of the Colleges categorized based on their marital status with regard to their scores on Self Awareness, as one of the components of Emotional Competence. The mean value of the unmarried Principals has been found to be greater than that of married Principals. Hence, it is concluded that the unmarried principals possess more of Self-Awareness when compared to their married counter parts. It is also found that there is no significant difference between the means of the Principals of Colleges of Education on the scores of the most of the dimension of emotional competence of the principals irrespective of their sex and marital status as well as the locality and type of the institution. It is also found that there is significant and positive correlation at 0.01 level among different components of Emotional Competence viz. Self-Awareness and Self-Management & Relationship-Management, Self-Management and Social Awareness & Relationship-Management, Social Awareness and Self-Management &

Relationship-Management. However, there is no significant relationship between Self-Awareness and Social Awareness, Social Awareness and Relationship Management.

Keywords: emotional competence, self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship management

1. Introduction

“A learned capability based on emotional intelligence that results in outstanding performance at work. Our emotional intelligence determines our potential for learning the practical skills based on the five elements: self-awareness, motivation, self-regulation, empathy, and adeptness in relationships. Our emotional competence shows how much of that potential we have translated into on-the-job capabilities.” (Goleman, 1970). Richard Boyatzis says *“the twenty competence are emotional self-awareness, accurate self-assessment, self-confidence, emotional self-control, trustworthiness, adaptability, achievement orientation, initiative, conscientiousness, empathy, organizational awareness, service orientation, developing others, inspirational leadership, change catalyst, influence, conflict management, team work and collaboration, communication and building bonds.”* This paper aims at finding out the inter-correlation among the different dimensions of Emotional Competence and how they differ among themselves in terms of certain variables viz. sex and marital status of the Principals of the Colleges of Education and the locality and type of institutions.

2. Different Dimensions of Emotional Competence

According to Richard Boyatzis, the components of Emotional Competence have been described as follows:

- Self-Awareness: Capacity for understanding one’s emotions, one’s strengths, and one’s weaknesses.
- Self-Management: Capacity for effectively managing one’s motives and regulating one’s behaviour.
- Social Awareness: Capacity for understanding what others are saying and feeling and why they feel and act as they do.
- Relationship Management: Capacity for acting in a way that gets desired results from other and reaches personal goals.

3. Need and Significance of the Study

In general, the Principals of the Colleges of Education in Tamil Nadu suffer a range of interpersonal and task demands in the carrying out their professional responsibilities in the context of carrying out their mandate demands. The roles being played by such Principals tend to be quite stressful to act effectively. But, at the same time, they respond to situations in which they find that the outcomes are not satisfying. The effect of their responses to such undesirable situations over a period of time lead them to face adverse effects on their professional commitments. Under these circumstances, there is a need for taking up a study in the context of academic administrators' Emotional Competence. Hence, the scholars interested in taking up a study related to academic administrators' Emotional Competence.

4. Review of Related Literature on Emotional Competence

Chan and David (1983) studied the emotional competence, social coping and psychological distress among Chinese gifted students in Hong Kong. The study shows that emotional competence was negatively related to psychological distress.

Brown and Schutte (1986) studied the relationship between emotional competence and subjective fatigue in New England University students. The findings of the study revealed that high emotional competence was associated with less fatigue.

Kiran and Lakshmi (1990) studied the emotional competencies of heroin users. The study revealed that normal persons have greater ability to function with emotions than heroin users.

Saarni (1999) studied the links between emotional competence, socialization and resilience. The findings showed that emotional competence is contributing to resilience.

Nada (2000) studied whether there is any relationship between emotional competence and academic success. It was revealed that there is a significant relationship between emotional competence and academic achievement.

Deane (2001) studied the relationship between emotional competence and willingness to seek help for emotional problems and suicidal ideation. The study revealed that there was no significant relationship between emotion perception skill and willingness to seek help.

Seema (2004) studied the relationship between emotional competence and occupational stress among elementary school teachers. The study shows that emotional competence plays a vital role in reducing stress in academic situation.

Palmer and Donaldson (2005) examined the relationship between emotional competence and life satisfaction. It was found that well conceptualized and developed emotional competence can account for the variance in life satisfaction.

Landa and Lopez (2006) analysed the emotional competence related to burnout among university teachers. It was found a strong negative correlation between emotional competence and burnout.

Day and Newsome (2007) studied the relationship of emotional competence, cognitive ability and personality with academic achievement. The findings of the study revealed that both emotional competence, cognitive ability and personality with academic achievement. It was revealed that both emotional competence and cognitive ability were significantly associated with academic achievement.

5. Statement of the Problem

Emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth (Salovey, Peter and David Sluyter, 1997). Hence, it is evident that for effective academic administration in educational institutions, it is indispensable to enhance the Emotional Competence among the academic administrators by taking up relevant and in-depth studies should be taken. Under these circumstances, the scholars have taken up the study entitled "*Emotional Competence of the Principals of Colleges of Education: A Correlation Study*".

5.1 Definition of the Key Term

"A learned capability based on emotional intelligence that results in outstanding performance at work. Our emotional intelligence determines our potential for learning the practical skills based on the five elements: self-awareness, motivation, self-regulation, empathy, and adeptness in relationships. Our emotional competence shows how much of that potential we have translated into on-the-job capabilities." (Goleman, 1970)

According to Hay McBer, emotional competence is a learned capability based on emotional intelligence that contributes to effective performance at work. This model combines the seminal work of Daniel Goleman. Richard Boyatzis with Hay McBer reported that the twenty competence are emotional self-awareness, accurate self-assessment, self-confidence, emotional self-control, trustworthiness, adaptability, achievement orientation, initiative, conscientiousness, empathy, organizational awareness, service orientation, developing others, inspirational leadership, change catalyst, influence, conflict management, team work and collaboration, communication

and building bonds. It is also found that there is no significant difference between the means of the principals of colleges of education on the scores of the most of the dimension of emotional competence of the principals irrespective of their sex and marital status as well as the locality and type of the institution.

5.2 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are stated as follows:

1. To study the extent of the Emotional Competence of the Principals of Colleges of Education.
2. To study whether gender difference exists in Emotional Competence among the Principals of Colleges of Education.
3. To study whether significant difference exists in Emotional Competence of the Principals of Colleges of Education with regard to the type and locale of the colleges.
4. To study whether significant difference exists in Emotional Competence of Principals of Colleges of Education with regard to the demographical variable viz. marital status.

5.3 Hypotheses of the Study

The study is designed with the following hypotheses:

1. There is significant gender difference in the scores of Emotional Competence (Dimension Wise) Principals of Colleges of Education.
2. There is significant difference in Emotional Competence (Dimension Wise) of the Principals of Colleges of Education with regard to the type of the colleges.
3. There is significant difference in Emotional Competence (Dimension Wise) with regard to the demographical variable viz. marital status.
4. There is significant correlation among the different dimensions of Emotional Competence of the Principals of Colleges of Education.

5.4 Tool Used for Data Collection

Emotional Competency Inventory for Teachers (Balasubramanian and Abilash Babu, 2009) has been used to collect the required data from the sample chosen. The inventory contains 20 positive items and 5 negative items. All the statements except statement numbers from 19 to 23 are positive. The number of items selected for the inventory falling under three major dimensions viz. Self-Awareness, Self-Management, Social Awareness and Relationship Management.

6. Scope and Delimitations of the Study

6.1 Scope of the study

It is to note that the findings of the study would be useful to the academic administrators, educationists, teachers, research scholars and the Principals of Colleges of Education to know the existence of Emotional Competence among their colleagues in the working environment.

6.2 Delimitations of the Study

Though care was taken to make the study as precise, comprehensive and objective as possible, certain limitations have adept into the study which are listed as follows:

1. In spite of the sample, being selected for the study is on a stratified random sampling basis, it represents a few percent of the total population of Principals of Colleges of Education in Tamilnadu.
2. The sample selected for the study does not cover the entire state, but confined to only three districts of the state viz. Erode, Tirupur and Coimbatore.
3. Emotional Competence is associated with a large number of variables. However, the present study has been delimited to include only four dimensions viz. Self-Awareness, Self-Management, Social Awareness and Relationship Management.

7. Brief Methodology of the Study

Descriptive Survey Method has been taken up for collection of the required data from the Principals of the Colleges of Education. In line with the Stratified Random Sampling Technique, 50 Principals of Colleges of Education from three districts of Tamilnadu state have been chosen for the study. Emotional Competency Inventory for Teachers (Balasubramanian and Abilash Babu, 2009) was used to collect the required data from the sample chosen with regard to Emotional Competency scores. The sample is comprised of male and female Principals with the age range between 30+ and 50 and above working in rural and urban areas.

7.1 Analysis of Data

Descriptive, differential and correlation studies have been taken up for the purpose of achieving the objectives of the study. Accordingly, mean and SD of the scores of Emotional Competence of the Principals has been computed. Besides descriptive studies, differential studies as well as correctional studies have also been taken up adopting "t" tests and Pearson's Product Moment Co-efficient of Correlation Method respectively. The details of the data analysis are given as follows:

7.1.1 Descriptive Study

The mean and SD of the Burnout scores of the sample have been computed for the different dimensions as well as for the total Burnout. The distribution of the said mean and SD are as given below:

Table 1: Distribution of Mean and SD of the Scores of Different Dimensions of Emotional Competence of the Principals of Colleges of Education

S.No	Components	Mean	S.D.	
1	Emotional Competence	Self-Awareness	27.06	3.65
2		Self-Management	56.86	5.83
3		Social Awareness	30.52	2.53
4		Relationship Management	71.42	8.08
		Total Score	185.86	15.42

From the Table 1, it is found that the scores are normally distributed and the values of the SD indicate that the sample is heterogeneous in nature.

7.2 Testing of Hypotheses

7.2.1 Differential Studies

In order to test the formulated hypothesis, 't' tests have been attempted between means of the scores of the Principals of Colleges of Education categorized in terms of their sex and marital status as well as locality and type of the institution on the scores of various dimensions of Emotional Competence. The mean and S.D. of the scores of the various dimensions of Emotional Competence have already been computed. The results are given in the Table 2.

Table 2: Significance of Difference between the Means of the Scores of the Different Components of Emotional Competence of the Principals of the Colleges of Education Classified in Terms of Sex, Marital Status of the Principals and Locality and Type of Colleges

S. No.	Components of Emotional Competence	Main Variables	Sub-variables	N	Mean	S.D.	't'
1	Self-Awareness	Sex	Male	28	26.54	3.73	1.15 ^{NS}
			Female	22	27.73	3.50	
		Locality of College	Rural	29	27.07	3.65	0.02 ^{NS}
			Urban	21	27.05	3.73	
		Nature of College	Co-Ed.	44	27.14	3.38	0.27 ^{NS}
			Non Co-Ed.	6	26.50	5.61	
Marital Status	Married	47	26.94	3.72	2.60*		
	Unmarried	3	29.00	1.00			

S. No.	Components of Emotional Competence	Main Variables	Sub-variables	N	Mean	S.D.	't'
2	Self-Management	Sex	Male	28	57.32	5.36	0.614 ^{NS}
			Female	22	56.27	6.45	
		Locality of College	Rural	29	56.83	5.73	0.040 ^{NS}
			Urban	21	56.90	6.09	
		Nature of College	Co-Ed.	44	56.66	5.68	0.549 ^{NS}
			Non Co-Ed.	6	58.33	7.17	
Marital Status	Married	47	57.09	5.81	1.070 ^{NS}		
	Unmarried	3	53.33	5.85			
3	Social Awareness	Sex	Male	28	30.96	2.16	1.37 ^{NS}
			Female	22	29.95	2.87	
		Locality of College	Rural	29	30.55	2.06	0.09 ^{NS}
			Urban	21	30.48	3.10	
		Nature of College	Co-Ed.	44	30.48	2.30	0.21 ^{NS}
			Non Co-Ed.	6	30.83	4.07	
Marital Status	Married	47	30.55	2.57	0.51 ^{NS}		
	Unmarried	3	30.00	1.73			
8	Relationship Management	Sex	Male	28	71.61	7.72	0.18 ^{NS}
			Female	22	71.18	8.68	
		Locality of College	Rural	29	70.90	8.06	0.53 ^{NS}
			Urban	21	72.14	8.24	
		Nature of College	Co-Ed.	44	71.77	8.24	0.96 ^{NS}
			Non Co-Ed.	6	68.83	6.82	
Marital Status	Married	47	71.68	7.90	0.63 ^{NS}		
	Unmarried	3	67.33	11.67			

*Significant at 0.05 level;

N.S. – Not Significant

From the Table 2 it is found that there is significant difference at 0.05 level between the means of the scores of the Principals of the Colleges categorized based on their marital status with regard to their scores on Self Awareness, as one of the components of Emotional Competence. The mean value of the unmarried Principals has been found to be greater than that of married Principals. Hence, it is concluded that the unmarried principals possess more of Self-Awareness when compared to their married counter parts.

It is also found that there is no significant difference between the means of the principals of colleges of education on the scores of the most of the dimension of emotional competence of the principals irrespective of their sex and marital status as well as the locality and type of the institution.

Hence, the hypothesis has been restated that sex and marital status of the principals and the locality and type of the institution have no influence on most of the components of Emotional Competence.

7.2.2 Correlation Studies

In order to test the hypothesis “*There is significant correlation among the different dimensions of Burnout of the Principals of Colleges of Education*”, an attempt was made to find out the inter correlation co-efficient among the scores of various dimensions of Burnout of the Principals of Colleges of Education. The results are given in the Table: 3.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix among the Scores of Different Dimensions of Emotional Competency of the Principals of Colleges of Education

Components of Emotional Competence	E ₁	E ₂	E ₃	E ₄
E ₁	–	0.51*	0.18	0.31*
E ₂	0.51*	–	0.48*	0.55*
E ₃	0.18 ^{NS}	0.49*	–	0.22 ^{NS}
E ₄	0.31*	0.55*	0.22 ^{NS}	–

*Significant at 0.01 level; N.S.: Not Significant

E₁: Self-Awareness;

E₂: Self-Management;

E₃: Social-Awareness;

E₄: Relationship Management.

From Table 3 it is found that there is significant and positive correlation at 0.01 level among different components of Emotional Competence viz. Self-Awareness and Self-Management & Relationship-Management, Self-Management and Social Awareness & Relationship-Management, Social Awareness and Self-Management & Relationship-Management. However, there is no significant relationship between Self-Awareness and Social Awareness, Social Awareness and Relationship Management.

Hence, the scholars restated the hypothesis that some of the components of the Emotional Competence have positive relationship among themselves while some of the components have no relationship at all.

8. Educational Implications of the Study

The educational implications of the study are given as follows:

1. Educational Administrators may take into consideration that unfavourable Emotional Competence hinders effective administration of the educational institutions.

2. Lack of Emotional Competence prevents the effective academic administration and hence, studies related to effective management of Emotional Competence may be encouraged among academic administrators.
3. Counselling sessions may also be organized to the academic administrators with a view to aiding them how to develop their Emotional Competence for effective functioning at the institutional environment.
4. Awareness of the knowledge of sources of Emotional Competence may support the educational administrators at the higher level how to enhance the same among their subordinates.
5. Higher the level of Emotional Competence of the academic administrators in the working environment, higher will be their outcome in achieving the envisaged objectives.

9. Suggestions for Further Research

The suggestions for further studies in the area of Emotional Competence are given as follows:

1. The professional involvement and professional advancement of the academic administrators having different level of Emotional Competence may be studied.
2. The organizational commitment of the academic administrators with differing levels of Emotional Competence may be studied.
3. Studies related to self-esteem of the academic administrators having different levels of Emotional Competence may also be taken up.

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